

Supplementary

Supplement 1 - Backbone RMSD distributions during the three replica trajectories

(different color curves) of MD simulations using CHARMM36m forcefield. Overlap indicates convergence. The numbers below the graphs indicate the lengths of trajectories in ns for replicas 1, 2, 3 and ff14sb (in brackets).

Supplement 2 - Potential energies of linker-linker interactions calculated using CHARMM36m and ff14SB forcefields from solvated trajectories modified to contain only linker atoms. The error bars

Supplement 3 - ratio of microstates accessible to the global energy minimum microstate within 1, 2 or 5 kT. Calculated on a PMF curve of terminal capping residue distances using CHARMM36 MD forcefield simulations.

Supplement 4 - ratio of microstates accessible to the global energy minimum microstate within 1, 2 or 5 kT. Calculated on a PMF curve of terminal capping residue distances using ff14SB MD forcefield simulations.

Supplement 5 - percentual contributions to the total free energy of the linkers. The darker shade of red represents more negative contributions, darker blue represents more positive contributions.